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ABSTRACT

There is a long history of conducting experimental tests of hydraulic problems, from Archimedes, Leonardo da Vinci and the great 19th century pioneers such as Froude and Reynolds, right up until the present day. Throughout this time, hydraulic scale models have proven to be an effective and cost-efficient tool to investigate complex dynamic problems following the principle of similitude.

The use of physical hydraulic models has evolved, and will continue to evolve, as computer power increases. Physical models today capture orders of magnitude more data than they did even a decade ago. Terrestrial and underwater laser scanners, photogrammetry, acoustic and optical sensors are gathering Gigabytes of data at a time over fast ethernet networks and storing them on large servers. Sophisticated data processing and analysis routines are used to extract more information (on damage or scour or vessel movement) than was previously possible. These outputs from physical models are still used in the design and verification of many structures, ranging from traditional seawalls, revetments, dykes and levees, through weirs and river control structures, to floating bodies, marine foundations and renewable energy devices.

However, increasing emphasis is being given to complex, turbulent flows, with more linear problems being taken over almost exclusively by numerical models. The increasing capability of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models is the latest challenge to physical models. This is hampered by the fact that there are so many CFD solvers, and methods to set up and run models, that a wide range of answers can be given. Physical models, on the other hand, have a history of over a century of successful development and produce more detailed results than ever before. Moreover, techniques and protocols for composite modelling – which uses both physical and numerical models together – are being developed. The continued development of numerical and physical models in parallel – to compare and complement each other, to utilize the strengths and minimize the weaknesses of each – is therefore expected to continue. As a consequence, consultants, contractors and clients are all expected to retain a need for physical models to address problems in structural design and environmental fluid mechanics for many years to come.

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1 INTRODUCTION

There is a long history of conducting experimental tests of hydraulic problems, from Archimedes, Leonardo da Vinci and the great 19th century pioneers such as Froude and Reynolds, right up until the present day. Throughout this time, hydraulic scale models have proven to be an effective and cost-efficient tool to investigate complex dynamic problems following the principle of similitude (Yalin, 1971, Hughes, 1993, Heller, 2011). The 20th century saw the development of many of the great hydraulics and hydrodynamics laboratories that remain in use to this day, such as:

- Hamburgische Schiffbau-Versuchsanstalt GmbH, HSVA (Germany, 1913)
- Delft Hydraulics, now known as Deltares (NL, 1927);
- Waterways Experiment Station (USA, 1929);
- National Research Council Hydraulics Lab, Ottawa (Canada, 1945);
- Port and Harbour Research Institute (Japan, 1946);
- Laboratoire National D'Hydraulique (France, 1946);
- Hydraulics Research Station, now known as HR Wallingford (UK, 1947);
- Centro de Estudios y Experimentación de Obras Públicas, CEDEX (Spain, 1957);
- Danish Hydraulics Institute (Denmark, 1964);
- MARINTEK Large Ocean Basin (Norway, 1981);
- Coastal Research Center - Forschungszentrum Küste (Germany, 1983).

Physical modelling has been used as a design tool for river, coastal and marine structures worldwide since the foundation of the laboratories above, and many others not reported here. Indeed, the prevalence of hydraulics laboratories in Universities and Research Institutes across the world is testimony to the continued importance and influence of physical model testing in hydraulics today. This history and practice of hydraulic modelling has been reported in many books and papers, including those by Yalin (1971), Hudson et al (1979), Ivicic (1980), Dalrymple (1985), Martins (1989), Hughes (1993), Chakrabarti (1994), Frostick *et al.* (2011), Frostick *et al.* (2014) and Aberle *et al.* (2019).

The increasing rise of computing power means that this position is changing (Sutherland and Evers, 2013). 2D (depth-averaged) numerical flow models are becoming replaced by more detailed 3D flow models or even computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models. This has increased the range of problems that can be addressed satisfactorily using numerical models. For example, back in the 1970's the modelling of tides, flooding or sediment transport in an estuary or large river would normally have been undertaken using a physical model (such as the model of the Exe from 1974 shown in Figure 1). Today, such studies are almost always conducted using numerical models – with the exceptions being some very large scale models, such as

- the model of the Oder at Hohenwutzen at the Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute (BAW) in Germany (Henning *et al.* 2008).
- Nanjing Hydraulic Research Institute physical models of the Three Gorges dam and various harbours and rivers.

Figure 1: Physical model of flooding of the Exe from 1974

However, physical modelling has been evolving alongside computational modelling (Aberle *et al.*, 2019). The main reason for this is that Moore's law (which states that computer power doubles about every 18 months) also applies to the equipment used to generate the input conditions to a physical model and to measure the resulting flows, sediment transport and bathymetry. The increases in computer power, the development of ethernet technologies for transferring data and the shrinking of electronics mean that more and more detailed measurements at finer resolution and higher frequencies can be measured in physical models and in the field (Sutherland and Evers, 2013, Aberle *et al.*, 2019). This has allowed more detailed investigations of increasingly complex phenomena to be undertaken. This trend is expected to continue and new measuring techniques are being developed, allowing physical measurements at a greater spatial density. Knowledge of model scaling is also developing (Hughes, 1993, Rijn *et al.*, 2011, Heller, 2011, Heller, 2017, Henry & Aberle, 2018) which improves our understanding of the applicability of model results.

As a result, there has been a trend for computer models taking over the simulation of flow and wave conditions that are linear, or close to linear, while physical models remain dominant in areas with strong non-linearity. There has also been an increase in the combined use of physical and numerical models – also known as hybrid or composite modelling - (Sutherland and Barfuss, 2011, Gerritsen and Sutherland, 2011) to address problems in structural design and environmental fluid mechanics.

Physical models can also play an important role in adapting to climate change. Numerical models used for climate change impact analysis cannot be validated against field measurements for conditions beyond the range of the current climate. Since we have no field data truly reflecting future conditions, a key challenge in climate change adaptation is to rigorously test models using proxies of future conditions. Physical modelling offers the opportunity to test present-day situations and possible climate change adaptations against a range of hydraulic boundary conditions, such as

water level, wave height and flow speed, that exceed present day conditions and are compatible with climate change projections.

This report, which forms deliverable D7.5 of the HYDRALAB plus project, includes the contents prepared by the HYDRALAB consortium for its website <https://hydralab.eu//> in order to engage with contractors (and consultants) who could have a use for a physical hydraulic model. The purpose of the content is to showcase how useful physical modelling can be for the design of infrastructure. Therefore, this deliverable shows how physical models are being used today to address practical problems in the design and operation of various developments and infrastructures. The following sections describe:

- the main areas of physical testing undertaken in commercial European laboratories;
- how physical models are increasingly used with numerical models to address practical concerns.

It does not cover academic research, the emerging field of eco-hydraulics (Frostick *et al.*, 2014, Luz Fernandez *et al.*, 2019) or the more detailed, specialist equipment that is generally confined to research projects (e.g. O'Donoghue and Schimmels, 2018).

2 PHYSICAL MODEL TESTING

Physical model testing plays an important part in the development and validation of the design of many coastal, maritime and freshwater hydraulic structures. Some of the most commonly forms of structures tested in hydraulic laboratories include breakwaters and floating structures. These may, of course, be combined in the design of a new harbour or marina or could be completely separate. Some examples of phenomena tested are given in the sections below.

2.1 WAVE OVERTOPPING OF STRUCTURES

Waves passing over the top of a structure can cause damage and disruption to the structure itself and to assets being protected by that structure. Different types of activity and structure have different acceptable overtopping rates (commonly expressed as the average volume of water to pass a metre length of the structure in each second). A range of conditions is likely to be tested, from those occurring several times a year – to determine safe operational conditions – to extreme design conditions and commonly, an overload condition.

An example of a wave overtopping test carried out in a wave flume, with random waves approaching straight onto the structure is shown in Figure 2. This type of test is known as a two-dimensional (2D) test. Three-dimensional (3D) tests can also be undertaken in wave basins (Figure 3). Often a 2D test at a larger scale (such as 1:20) is carries out in a flume, while a 3D test at a scale of 1:40 to 1:60 is carried out in a wave basin. Modern wave paddles, driven by electric motors, can be used to generate different standard wave spectra (such a Pierson-Moscowitz or Jonswap) or specialised spectra, such as combinations of swell (long period waves generated a long distance away) and wind-sea (with shorter period waves, generated more locally). In the case of three-dimensional tests, the wave conditions can be long-crested (coming from a single direction) or short-crested (coming from a range of directions). Wave conditions can even be varied along the face of a wave-maker to represent spatial variations in incident wave conditions.

Figure 2: Wave overtopping a seawall in a 2D model

Figure 3: Wave overtopping a breakwater in a 3D model

2.2 BREAKWATER STABILITY

Another common type of hydraulic test is the stability of a breakwater. These can be constructed from scaled rock or scaled concrete armour units (commonly hired from the patent holder) as shown in Figure 4. Rock sizes are scaled to take account of variations in the density of water and rock armour, while filter layer scaling also has to take account of permeability as well. Templates are normally used to get the correct cross-section of every layer, while concrete armour units often have to be placed in a specialised way to create the correct packing density.

The movement of armour can be measured using a range of methods. Traditionally, the elevation across a number of sections through a model has been measured using a point gauge. Increasingly terrestrial laser scanners or other optical techniques, such as photogrammetry or structure-from-motion (Westoby *et al.*, 2012, Todd *et al.*, 2016) have been used to create a three-dimensional digital elevation model (DEM) of the entire structure (Figure 5). It is possible to get much more detailed assessments of damage suffered using a DEM than using a few profiles.

Figure 4: Waves breaking on a physical model of a breakwater

Figure 5: Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of a breakwater roundhead, coloured using digital photographs

2.3 LOADS ON STRUCTURES

Loads on structures can be measured using a whole-body force table (Figure 6) or by pressure transducers (Figure 7). Whole body force tables can be used to measure forces and moment applied to a stiff model of the structure. A small degree of movement of the structure must be allowed, in order for forces to be registered.

Figure 6: Caisson with whole-body force measurements

Pressure measurements are conducted using an array of pressure transducers placed in the middle of the structure where the maximum pressures are commonly assumed to occur. In recent years the number of pressure sensors typically used has increased, with deployments of 16 to 32 becoming more common, due to advances in computers, data acquisition and sensor technology. Total forces are calculated by integrating the point measurements by assuming uniform pressure distribution between the sensors.

Figure 7: Three pressure transducers mounted on the face of a caisson (left) with detail of a pressure transducer (right)

For more complex studies the pressure distribution is significantly less well known and the calculated resultant force may vary quite considerably from the actual force (Alderson and Allsop, 2007, Cuomo *et al.*, 2010). Hence, there is a requirement to develop pressure measurement systems with high spatial and temporal resolution. This is already occurring through the application to hydraulics of matrix-based tactile sensors (Stagonas *et al.*, 2016).

2.4 MOTION OF SHIPS AND OTHER FLOATING STRUCTURES

Port activities are significantly influenced by environmental forces. Large amplitude motions induced by wave action on moored ships, for instances, may lead to the interruption of shipping operations or damage to the mooring system, port structures or other ships. Well-designed physical models of port and offshore terminals are a valuable tool to study the response of moored ships to different environmental conditions (waves, currents, wind) and design parameters (type of ship, load condition, mooring layout, water depth). In fact, despite being a simplified reproduction of the reality, physical models can reproduce the phenomena with the greatest influence on the behaviour of moored ships in harbours under wind, current and wave forcing. These include the non-linear effects related to the propagation of waves to shallower waters and their interaction with coastal structures, and to the mooring system (Sutherland and Evers, 2013).

The physical modelling of floating bodies relies on being able to measure the motion of the body and also to being able to constrain it using mooring lines and fenders. Each method is described below.

2.4.1 Motion of floating bodies

Motions of floating bodies may be measured using different technologies, such as gyroscopes, accelerometers, potentiometers, laser, optical systems or mechanical systems. Mechanical measurement of motion (with magnetostrictive sensors for instance or weights and pulleys) induces mass, stiffness and damping effects that corrupt the original phenomenon. Therefore, measurements of motion should ideally be performed by robust and non-contacting systems, to avoid any interference with the physical model response.

Six Degree of Freedom (6-DOF) motions (i.e. surge, sway, yaw, heave, roll and pitch) of free floating or moored vessels or structures can be determined by laser displacement sensors or a real-time optical tracking system (Figure 8). The core components of an optical tracking system are:

- Two or more high-resolution and high-speed infrared video cameras;
- a number of small, lightweight reflective marks rigidly fixed to the model;
- a high speed network; and
- a data acquisition and processing unit.

Figure 8: Optical tracking system used to determine six degree of freedom movement of a model ship

The principle of operation consists of exposing the reflective marks to the infrared light emitted by the cameras and to detect the light reflected, although it is also possible to use active marks, able to emit infrared light. Each camera measures a 2D position of the reflective marks. The system combines processed data from two or more calibrated cameras to calculate 3D position of the markers. If several markers are attached to the model (ship or floating structure) its six degrees of freedom motions may be calculated in real-time. The accuracy of the system within a measuring area of length = 10 m and breadth = 10 m can be better than ± 1 mm for translational motions and $\pm 0.1^\circ$ for rotational movements.

Inertial measurement units (IMUs) featuring solid state accelerometers and gyroscopes are becoming increasingly accurate. The same units that are used on drones, gliders and industrial machinery can be used in physical models. Speed (rotational or linear) and displacement can be determined from single and double integration of acceleration with considerable accuracy, allowing

six degree of freedom motions to be determined.. These units can be installed within structures and / or where optical access is difficult.

Also shown in Figure 8 are a number of tripods with capacitive wave gauges to measure time series of surface elevation at a point. The gauges inside the harbour are used to check the level of wave energy entering the harbour.

2.4.2 Mooring lines

Mooring lines are often replicated by inserting springs into zero or low stretch lines (steel cable or Kevlar for instance) these lines will incorporate either an in-line load-cell or a cantilever load cell for measurement of the force, as shown in Figure 9. Alternatively, or in combination, mooring lines may be modelled as geometrically downscaled realistic lines.

The springs that are inserted are matched to ensure that the overall line elasticity is as close as possible to the desired characteristic. For more accurate models this involves building a series of extension-limited springs and coupling them together to approximate a non-linear characteristic. The limitation of this technique is that it can only model increasing stiffness curves.

In general, single stage linear approximations are used as these are the simplest, however in situations that require more accurate matching, two and very occasionally three stage approximations are used. These multiple extension-limiting springs are individually hand built and documented and are time consuming to produce.

Figure 9: Mooring lines and fenders used for ship mooring

2.4.3 Fenders

Fenders are flexible elements between ships and quay walls or between ships moored alongside, which usually behave as non-linear springs in compression. When testing floating objects resting against fenders the location and the stiffness characteristics of the fenders must be carefully represented in the model.

Two main types of fenders are currently used:

- Cylindrical Fenders with radial loading. This type has increasing reaction forces with compression and are generally soft for low loads as they react by ‘flexing of the rubber’ or by the compression of air for pneumatic fenders.
- Buckling fenders which can be axially loaded cylinders/cones or similar. These fenders are initially stiff as the reaction is created by compression of the material. When a certain load is exceeded the fender will start to buckle and the fender will react with a gradually reducing force until the buckling process stops and a sharp rise of the reaction force again appears.

Fenders are frequently modeled by a linear spring, which is acceptable for small values of compression around a mean position. When the total capacity of the fenders is used the non-linearities must be represented. This can be done mechanically in various ways.

2.5 SCOUR AT STRUCTURES

The presence of a structure causes flow speeds (whether caused by waves or currents) to increase locally. This can lead to increased rates of sediment transport and scour – the local lowering of the bed level around the structure. It is important for the design of many structures that the potential depth of scour is known and, in cases where deep scour cannot be tolerated, prevented using a form of scour protection. This can come in the form of rock armour, concrete units, concrete mattresses, rock filled bags, geotextile containers filled with sand, rock filled gabions or frond mats.

The depth of scour is often investigated using a physical model, with these studies often including the stability of scour protection designs. In recent years there has been increasing investment on marine renewable energy devices and this has led to a large number of physical model tests of the foundations of these devices – particularly in the testing of offshore wind turbine foundations. The original foundations for these devices were almost always monopoles, but as wind farms move into deeper water, a wider array of foundations, such as steel jackets and concrete gravity base structures are being tested.

About fifteen years ago the depth of scour and the movement of scour protection were normally measured using a mechanical bed profiler, which moved along a beam making regular measurements of the depth to the seabed or armour. The spatial variation of scour around a foundation could be measured by moving the beam around the structure to survey along different radial lines. Alternative approaches involved burying thin, regularly-marked rods in the seabed and counting how many marks were exposed, or lowering the water level and recording the shoreline using an overhead camera. In recent years, technologies have been developed which collect a lot more data, often with considerably less human intervention.

These techniques include the use of terrestrial laser scanners or underwater laser scanners. An example of an underwater laser scanner is the ULS200s shown in Figure 10. A fan of laser light illuminates the seabed and the point of contact with the bed is recorded by the digital camera. This scanner uses a triangulation method to determine the seabed location. The scanner can be moved over the seabed on a 1-D beam or a 2D profiler to build up a detailed bathymetry, or rotated about its axis to scan over a swath of bathymetry. An example of a bathymetry built up using a 2-dimensional profiler and scanner is shown in Figure 11. An area of approximately 4 m by 4 m can be surveyed using this system with a spatial resolution of about 4 mm in about 20 minutes.

Other techniques, such as photogrammetry, structure from motion (Westoby *et al.*, 2012) terrestrial laser scanning and point probes can also be used to measure scour around a structure (Todd *et al.*, 2016). These techniques generally require the basin to be drained before scanning, although some photogrammetry has been done above and below water level in a still basin. It takes only a few minutes to set up a terrestrial laser scanner in a flume or basin (Figure 12) and between about 5 minutes and 20 minutes to complete a scan (depending on the make of scanner, area to be scanned and density of the point cloud required). Several scans can be taken of a large model, so that all sides can be covered, and then combined using software that matches common location from different scans (Figure 5).

Figure 10: Underwater Laser Scanner surveying a swath of bathymetry around an offshore foundation model

Figure 11: Bathymetry of scour hole (at full scale) determined from underwater laser scanner data from a physical model

Figure 12: It takes only a few minutes to set up a Terrestrial Laser Scanner in a flume or basin

2.6 OTHER MODEL TYPES

Physical models are also used today for: beach optimisation, seawater intakes and outfalls, spillways, drop shafts and other hydraulic structures. Examples of the first two are given below.

2.6.1 Beaches

Figure 13 shows waves creating a tombolo inshore from a detached offshore breakwater in a wave basin at HR Wallingford. The relative length of the breakwater and relative distance from the shoreline are important parameters in determining the response of the beach that can be tested in a physical model.

Figure 13: Waves passing a detached breakwater

2.6.2 Seawater intakes and outfalls

Seawater intakes and outfalls pose a number of design issues that can be addressed using physical models. These include:

- Flow distributions across an intake
- Vortex formation at intakes
- Head loss
- Outfall basin / weir performance
- Hydrodynamic loads
- Scour and bed protection.

Figure 14 shows a physical model of a pumping station intake, which is testing the distribution of flows across the pump bays and the vorticity of the flow entering the mouths of the pumps (at the ends of the six pipes at the left of the figure). These studies can also be done in CFD models today (Figure 15), when comparisons between physical models and CFD models are useful in establishing the validity of CFD solutions.

Two model outfalls are shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17. The stability of the seabed close to an outfall is a common issue that needs to be addressed in design. Where there is a head difference between the outfall and the sea level a stepped spillway (Figure 17) can be used to dissipate energy and prevent erosion.

Figure 14: Physical model of a pumping station

CFX

Figure 15: Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model of a pumping station

Figure 16: Physical model of an outfall

Figure 17: Physical model of a stepped outfall

3 COMBINED USE OF NUMERICAL AND PHYSICAL MODELS

Physical and numerical models both have limitations that can restrict their independent use. Composite modelling – the combined use of physical and numerical models - can lead to different forms of improvements: being able to model problems that cannot be modelled by either physical or numerical modelling alone; increasing quality at the same cost or obtaining the same quality at reduced cost, reducing uncertainty at the same cost and realising that uncertainty reduction is also a quality issue (Sutherland and Barfuss, 2011, Gerritsen and Sutherland, 2011). Common ways that numerical and physical models can be used together for design are listed below.

3.1 MODEL NESTING

Model nesting is the most commonly applied and traditional method of linking numerical and physical models. A global or regional numerical model provides the external boundary conditions for a smaller area, more detailed model, such as a physical model.

3.2 USE OF NUMERICAL MODEL TO DESIGN PHYSICAL MODEL

Many physical models are designed with the assistance of numerical models. Examples include:

- Coastal area numerical model set up to model a wave basin to optimise the positions of wavemakers and wave guides.
- Numerical modelling of the approach geometry for a dam model has been used to minimise the head box dimensions, while maintaining the correct approach flow (Sutherland and Barfuss, 2011). This reduced construction costs while increasing model size and reducing Reynolds number scale effects.

3.3 PHYSICAL MODEL OF ONE COMPONENT OF A SYSTEM

The more straightforward (less nonlinear) aspects of a hydraulic system may be modelled adequately using numerical models, yet there may be elements of particular complexity or unusual arrangement that cannot be modelled with confidence using a standard modelling approach. The composite modelling approach to such a problem involves the following stages:

1. Initial modelling of the system using one or more numerical models. This stage is used to optimize the layout as much as possible;
2. Physical modelling of the most complex part of the system with appropriate measurements to characterize the results;
3. Incorporation of the physical model results into the next round of numerical modelling either by parameterization of them or through their use in calibrating the numerical model.

One example involved the design of the approach to a lock system on a river (Bousmar et al, 2010):

- i. investigating the backwater effect of the new structure on the river flood flow using a 1D numerical model,
- ii. investigating the velocity field using a 2D numerical model and a physical model and

- iii. analysis of the flow pattern, in terms of fluidity and safety of navigation (using a navigation simulator).

The physical model was found more adequate than the 2D numerical model in turbulent conditions, although it was more difficult and time consuming to extract velocity measurements.

3.4 MODEL TRAINING AND CALIBRATION

A physical model can be used to calibrate a numerical model, which can then be run for different cases, or to obtain data where there were no physical model measurements. Alternatively, the physical model can be used to supply the data that goes into an artificial intelligence model, such as a neural network (Aamir & Ahmed, 2019). Possibly the model common use in design of coastal structures is the use of a neural network to train a simulator of wave overtopping rates (Eurotop, 2018).

4 SUMMARY

There is a long history of conducting experimental tests of hydraulic problems, from Archimedes, Leonardo da Vinci and the great 19th century pioneers such as Froude and Reynolds, right up until the present day. Throughout this time, hydraulic scale models have proven to be an effective and cost-efficient tool to investigate complex dynamic problems following the principle of similitude.

The use of physical hydraulic models has evolved, and will continue to evolve, as computer power increases. Physical models today capture orders of magnitude more data than they did even a decade ago. Terrestrial and underwater laser scanners, photogrammetry, acoustic and optical sensors are gathering Gigabytes of data at a time over fast ethercat networks and storing them on large servers. Sophisticated data processing and analysis routines are used to extract more information (on damage or scour or vessel movement) than was previously possible. These outputs from physical models are still used in the design and verification of many structures.

However, increasing emphasis is being given to complex, turbulent flows, with more linear problems being taken over almost exclusively by numerical models. The increasing capability of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models is the latest challenge to physical models. This is hampered by the fact that there are so many CFD solvers, and methods to set up and run models, that a wide range of answers can be given. Physical models, on the other hand, have a history of over a century of successful development and produce more detailed results than ever before. Moreover, composite modelling – which uses both physical and numerical models together – is developing. The continued development of numerical and physical models in parallel – to compare and complement each other, to utilize the strengths and minimize the weaknesses of each – is therefore expected to continue. As a consequence, consultants, contractors and clients are all expected to retain a need for physical models to address problems in structural design and environmental fluid mechanics for many years to come.

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